

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SAMPSON****FIRST NAME: EUNICE OGHOMWEN****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Pr. LAURENT CLEENEWERCK**

This paper uses US English (for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting of references).
The Rule of Style is: Turabian (footnotes). It uses Zotero for referencing.
The author uses the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8 and its 'References' feature.

ACA-401D COURSE ASSESSMENT QUIZ

1. **Today's Information Age fuels plagiarism, especially as information has become seemingly commonplace. As an academic researcher, why and how should you ensure that you avoid plagiarism?**
 - Plagiarism is a common occurrence in the information age; so, ensure that you cite the sources of very vital information.
 - Plagiarism could attract severe penalties, including failing grade and expulsion. You could avoid such dire consequences by ensuring that every work cited in your academic paper is properly referenced using the recommended style guide.¹**
 - Plagiarism makes a researcher's work difficult to read and comprehend. Make sure that you present the plagiarized texts in your own words.
 - Plagiarism is a big offence in some countries. Ensure that you reference sources for information from countries where there are strong regulations.

1. EUCLID University, ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1, 2015, 5. Accessed July 3, 2019. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

2. **The efforts that go into a dissertation are enormous. But these efforts could be wasted if the final report is poorly written and full of errors. Which of the following simple but critical steps must be taken to ensure that the final output makes reading easy and worthwhile for the report users?**

- Ensure that the final report is painstakingly proofread, well edited, and double-checked for spelling, structural and cohesion errors.²**
- Ensure that the final report is neatly printed and spiral bound.
- Ensure that the final report is published on Amazon and other major online book stores.
- Ensure that unauthorized persons are not given access to the final report.

3. **Online sources constitute arguably the biggest reference materials for today's research papers. But the risk of junk, unverifiable and unreliable information is also very high with online sources. What are the major points to ponder when ascertaining the reliability of online information?**

- Is the site owned by famous individuals?
- What is the daily average number of visits and traffic to the website?
- Is the site sponsored by a reputable organization or individual? Is it linked to a credible professional journal? Does it supplement a reliable print version? When last was the site updated?³**
- When was the last time you had a need to visit the site?

2. EUCLID University, ACA-401 Coursepack, 5.

3. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2013), 29.

4. **What are the key differences between author-date (in-text) citations and bibliography-style citations?**

- In bibliography-style citations, you use superscript numberings; while in author-date (in-text) citations you do not.
- In bibliography-style citations, the disclosure of author, title, publisher, place and year of publication is mandatory; while in author-date (in-text) citations, it is not.
- In bibliography-style citations, you list the Bibliography in alphabetical order using author's names; while in author-date (in-text) citations, you do not.
- In bibliography-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it; you then use notes (footnotes or end notes) to indicate the sources of the citations, using corresponding superscripted numbering. But in author-date (in-text) citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it, allowing the scholar to disclose within the text itself, part of the details of the source of information used in the paper. Full details of the citations are now listed at the end of the document as 'References.'**⁴

5. **What are the key segments and structural components that all dissertations must have?**

- All dissertations must have an introduction, review of relevant literature, review of methodology, presentation of findings, presentation of analysis and interpretation, and presentation of conclusions and recommendations.**⁵
- All dissertations must be long and grammatically correct.

4. Turabian, A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 29.

5. Linda Dale Bloomberg, and Marie F. Volpe, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 18.

- All dissertations must create space for readers' feedbacks.
 - All dissertations must be humorous and exciting to read.
6. **There are two broad approaches to a research project - Qualitative and Quantitative research. What are the basic considerations for determining which of the two approaches to apply?**
- Qualitative research is suited for “promoting a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants. This approach places emphasis on exploration, discovery, and description. Quantitative research, on the other hand, is applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena.” Your research objective determines which of the two approaches you adopt.⁶**
 - Qualitative research is best suited for projects that focus on modern trends; while Quantitative is best for projects that focus on historical trends.
 - Qualitative research is best suited for essays targeted at a young audience; while Quantitative is best for essays targeted at an older audience.
 - Qualitative research is best suited for long essays; while Quantitative is best for very short essays.
7. **Several researchers see the methodology chapter as the most problematic chapter to tackle in a dissertation. What are the basic components that should be in this chapter?**
- There are five key components that should be in the methodology chapter: “an overview of the research design, information needed and sources of data, proposed research sample, plans and**

6. Bloomberg, Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, 33-34.

- methods for data collection and data analysis, and a rationale for the methods to be used.”⁷**
- There are three key issues to include in the methodology chapter: who will read the report? What is the preference of the project supervisor? What is the age profile of the project defense panel?
 - There are two key issues to include in the methodology chapter: when will the report be published? What is the title of the report?
 - There are two key issues to include in the methodology chapter: who else has written on the topic? How many books are available on the topic?
8. **In today’s global environment where the issue of gender equality has taken on sensitive dimensions, how can you avoid offensive gender terminologies in your papers?**
- Since females are more often seen as the marginalized gender, you can use ‘she’ to always represent both genders, even for correspondences targeted at males.
 - Since there is no common agreement on the subject matter, you can use gender symbols instead of textual gender terms.
 - You can use gender neutral words to represent both genders. Instead of using the somewhat awkward ‘he/she,’ you can use generic plural forms such as ‘they,’ ‘everyone,’ firefighters, police officers, and so on.⁸**
 - Since it is a ‘*man’s world*,’ you can use ‘he’ to always represent both genders, even for correspondences that are addressed to females.

7. Bloomberg, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 19.

8. European Commission Directorate-General for Translation, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 47, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/>.

9. **What guide does the Turabian style give on how to quote a long text?**

- Double-space and indent all texts that are five lines or longer.
- Paraphrase all quotes that are long and span across several paragraphs.
- Do not use in-text citation for a quote that is too long.
- Present a prose quotation of five or more lines as a block quotation; use single-spacing; indent the entire quotation as far as you indent the first line of a paragraph; and do not add quotation marks at the beginning or end.⁹**

10. **In a well written dissertation, an abstract should be:**

- A carefully worded summary that precedes the main body of the report, that tells readers what to expect in other parts of the report and helps them determine if reading the entire report is worth their while.¹⁰**
- A long essay on how the report achieved its set objectives.
- A strong recommendation on how the report findings should be interpreted.
- A summary of related literature.

⁹ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 209.

¹⁰ Bloomberg, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 168.

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